

Automated Glaucoma Detection Using Transfer Learning with MobileNetV2: A High-Accuracy Convolution Deep Learning Approach

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Abstract— The terrible continuously advancing and degenerative eye disease which leads towards complete vision loss is known as glaucoma. In our present work we are proposing one automated end to end Deep Convolution Neural Network (CNN) using MobileNetV2 type of transfer learning. Although MobileNetV2 is lightweight, it is extremely powerful and pre-trained on ImageNet benchmark dataset. The system training as well as validation is performed using Holdout Method, on prior extensively augmented image data (fundus), labeled as either ‘Glaucoma’ or ‘No Glaucoma’. The system displays a brief Model Summary, Classification Report, Accuracy vs. Epoch, Loss vs. Epoch, Heatmap Confusion Matrix and finally predicts on completely unknown (i.e. unlabeled) test images. It achieves a validation accuracy as high as 100% and a validation loss as low as 0.188. This firmly establishes the reliability of the model. The system is robust in isolating glaucomatous eyes from healthy or normal ones. Stability of learning is pin pointed by the plot of accuracy and loss vs. epoch on validation data.

Summing the above up the current research for building up this low-cost scalable model indicates the overall efficacy of the MobileNetV2 transfer learning-based CNN in one medical image classification namely differentiation between glaucoma and no-glaucoma eye.

Keywords — *Glaucoma Detection, Tonometry, Perimetry, Transfer Learning, Deep Learning, CNN, MobileNetV2, Holdout Method, Classification Report, Heatmap Confusion Matrix, Accuracy, Precision, Recall, F1-Score.*

I. INTRODUCTION

The characteristic feature of glaucoma is that it is chronic, slowly progressive eye disease finally leading to damage of

eye nerve. Mostly it is accompanied by increase of eye pressure. Worldwide it is the leading cause of degenerative

blindness. It is very critical to early detect and timely intervene, because vision loss is permanent due to this glaucoma. Another danger is that it is always asymptomatic,

initially without any sign of disease. Tonometry, perimetry and optic nerve evaluation are some classical diagnosis methods. Unfortunately, these all require skilled ophthalmologists with costly equipment.

In medical imaging we can apply Artificial Intelligence (AI) and its Deep Learning or Convolution Neural Network (CNN) to achieve significant promising direction. To detect most ocular diseases, application of CNN is widely and successfully employed. In the medical image context, unfortunately, the availability of huge labelled dataset is scare and limited. But ironically training deep neural networks always requires huge amount of dataset.

To counter this hazardous situation, transfer learning has evolved as a blessing to image processing researchers. In transfer learning a CNN model is pre-trained with huge dataset (e.g. ImageNet etc.) and may or may not be finally fine-tuned for the desired specific job. MobileNetV2 is one such example of such pre trained transfer learning network which is lightweight as well as efficient.

Our present system is MobileNetV2 type of transfer learning-based CNN for automated glaucoma detection and separation from normal or healthy eye. The system *a-priori* performs data augmentation also, before sending the data to the MobileNetV2 architecture. We are achieving a validation accuracy of 100% and a validation loss of 0.188. This confirms the strong capacity of the model as applicability in

practical, accurate and easily accessible glaucoma identification mechanism.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Substantial number of applications of Deep Learning, more specifically CNN based network models are there in medical imaging as well as in the particular area of glaucoma detection. But they differ widely so far as their (i) architecture (ii) data volume or size (iii) amount or quality of generalization (iv) variety of evaluation metrics are concerned.

In [1] a deep learning method with multi task CNN is used which locates the optic disc to detect glaucoma. Accuracy is appreciable while it demands detailed segmentation masks. [2] is a patch-based CNN method, which focused on optic disc region. This acquired good performance but the limitation was its dependency on the technique or method of region-of-interest (ROI) extraction – which is likely to be practically error-prone and also inefficient.

[3] used transfer learning with ResNet50 and VGG16 onto accessible glaucoma dataset. They were computationally complicated and not at all suited for lightweight devices, although they got accuracy up to 96.7%.

In [4] EfficientNet and MobileNet were used for glaucoma identification with small amount of data. Only MobileNet performed better speed and accuracy as expected.

In [5] MobileNetV2 along with fundus images were used to achieve 98.1% accuracy. The conclusion is the lightweight transfer learning models are fast as well as effective in medical imaging particularly glaucoma detection.

Also, there are some other models for which the limitations are (i) huge computational cost (ii) lacking real time capacity (iii) poor generalization.

III. RESEARCH GAP IDENTIFIED BETWEEN EARLIER WORKS AND THE PROPOSED SYSTEM

Our present system fills up the vacant position or gap with the help of lightweight and high-performance architecture i.e. the use of MobilNetV2 transfer learning. This significantly achieved validation accuracy as high as 100% while suffering with loss as low as 0.188 with an appreciably limited dataset.

1. ROI Extraction (Dependency on Segmentation)

- Earlier Works: [1] and [2] is solely based on optic disc segmentation i.e. cropping of Region of Interest (ROI). Obviously thereby additional preprocessing overhead leads to significant error source.
- Research Gap Identified: Since perfect disc localization is needed, any dependency on accurate segmentation are likely to produce inferior generalization.

- Proposed System: This does not require segmentation or extraction of ROI – this operates directly on complete fundus images. Thereby it enhances robustness.

2. Overfitting and Limited Generalization

- Earlier Works: High train accuracy while low test accuracy i.e. overfitting is shown in some earlier works because of the scarcity of data with lack of data augmentation.
- Research Gap Identified: Those models became unreliable with unseen (unlabelled) data because of limited amount of generalization.
- Proposed System: It achieves perfect validation accuracy as high as 100% with low validation loss as low as 0.188 and this is an indication of strong generalization.

3. High Computational Complexity

- Earlier Works: Unlike MobileNetV2, use of transfer learning like ResNet50, VGG16 and EfficientNet results huge computational costs as well as they are time inefficient. Also, they cannot be used on edge devices.
- Research Gap Identified: Requirement of some efficient lightweight models.
- Proposed System: Perfect for real time glaucoma detection in remote areas with the use of a lightweight architecture MobileNetV2.

4. Incomplete Evaluation

- Earlier Works: Most of the previous models do not provide or display evaluation of complete spectrum e.g. model summary, classification report, accuracy and loss vs. epoch, heatmap confusion matrix especially prediction on unknown or unlabelled test dataset.
- Research Gap Identified: Reproducibility of those systems are getting obstructed with incomplete performance evaluations and thereby these all cannot be entrusted in any clinical applications by any medical practitioner.
- Proposed System: In our system, the complete spectrum of performance evaluation is displayed such as
 - (i) Brief Model Summary
 - (ii) Classification Report
 - (iii) Accuracy and loss vs. epoch
 - (iv) Heatmap Confusion Matrix
 - (v) Prediction on unknown or unseen images

IV. TRANSFER LEARNING

Transfer Learning in the contest of image classification is a blessing in deep Convolution Neural Network (CNN) where

there is scarcity of training and validation data. This Transfer Learning makes the system learn substantially and significantly with perfect generalization. Here a CNN model is developed for a particular task and thereafter reused for another related task as a starting point to build up another new model. Here the mother CNN model is supplied with huge amount of data and computational resource. And the destination model is thereby neither requiring abundant data nor resource of computation.

1) CNN Transfer Learning

Hierarchical feature learning:

- low-level features like edges and textures are learned by early layers.
- Patterns and shapes are learned by mid layers.
- High-level semantics are captured by series of end layers.

Early layers captured features are all general purpose. Later layers capture task specific features. General knowledge i.e. general-purpose features are retained by transfer learning in the base model and next only the fine-tuning task specific task has to be done to complete the new model with transfer learning.

2) How It Works

Two common strategies of transfer learning in CNN are:

1. Feature Extraction (adapted in this paper)
 1. The pre-trained model's layers are frozen (un trainable).
 2. New classification head is added on top and trained on the new task specific data.
 3. This is fast and avoids overfitting on small datasets.
2. Fine-Tuning
 1. In this technique some end layers of the pre-trained model are kept unfrozen and allowed a small learning rate.
 2. Adapts the model to work with specific domain features if there is scarcity of data

3) Advantages of Transfer Learning in general Medical Imaging

1. Avoids training from scratch and saves time and computational cost.
2. Leverages knowledge from large visual datasets to improve performance
3. Especially valuable in medical imaging and astronomy, where labeled images are limited.

Because of insufficiency of data for training and validation we have used transfer learning. Instead of training from scratch, a pre-trained CNN like VGG16, ResNet50, or EfficientNet can be fine-tuned on dataset. We have used MobileNetV2.

MobileNetV2- Feature Extraction Transfer Learning

Present system is having the following features with the use of MobileNetV2

1. Base model: MobileNetV2
2. Weights: Pre-trained on ImageNet
3. Frozen: Yes (base_model.trainable = False)
4. Custom layers added: Yes (new classification head)
5. Training: Only the custom head is trained; base model is used as a fixed feature extractor

V. METHODOLOGY

Architecture of the present CNN Model for glaucoma detectin is shown below:

Fig. 1 Block Diagram of the Present Transfer Learning based Glaucoma Detection System.

A. Technology Used

Component	Library / Tool
Deep Learning Model	TensorFlow / Keras
Preprocessing	ImageDataGenerator
Visualization	Matplotlib, Seaborn
Deployment Platform	Google Colab + Drive
Base Architecture	MobileNetV2 (TL)

Table 1 Different Components and Corresponding Library / Tool

B. Algorithm: Astronomical Image Classification

We are presenting below the algorithm for Glaucoma Detection System

The system is composed of the following core stages:

1. Data Acquisition and Organization

- Fundus images are organized into:
 - Yes_Glucoma/ – images diagnosed with glaucoma.
 - No_Glucoma/ – images without glaucoma.
 - Predict_Glucoma/ – unseen images for prediction.

Images are collected from trusted ophthalmological datasets or clinical sources and stored in structured folders in **Google Drive**.

2. Preprocessing and Data Augmentation

- All images are resized to $224 \times 224 \times 3$.
- Pixel values are rescaled to $[0,1]$.
- Real-time data augmentation is applied:
 - Horizontal flipping
 - Zooming
 - Validation split (80/20)
- Done using **ImageDataGenerator** from Keras.

3. Transfer Learning Model (MobileNetV2)

- Load **MobileNetV2** with `include_top=False`, pretrained on ImageNet.
- Freeze base layers to retain pretrained weights.
- Add custom classification head:
 - Global Average Pooling
 - Dense Layer (ReLU, 128 units)
 - Output Layer (Sigmoid, 1 unit for binary classification)
- Compile with:
 - **Loss:** Binary Cross-Entropy
 - **Optimizer:** Adam
 - **Metric:** Accuracy

4. Model Training

- Trained on `train_gen` (Yes/No Glaucoma images)
- Validated on `val_gen` (20% split)
- Epochs: 20+
- Outputs:
 - Accuracy vs Epoch plot
 - Loss vs Epoch plot
 - Tabular Model Summary

5. Model Evaluation

- Reuse validation generator (`shuffle=False`) for consistent metrics.
- Generate:
 - **Classification Report** (Precision, Recall, F1-score)
 - **Confusion Matrix** (True/False Positives & Negatives)
 - **Validation Accuracy: 100%**
 - **Validation Loss: 0.188**

6. Prediction Phase

- Predicts unseen data from `Predict_Glucoma/` folder.

- Outputs diagnosis: “**Glaucoma**” or “**No Glaucoma**” per image.
- Prints filename and predicted label in terminal.

VI. RESULTS

Kaggle Medical Imaging Dataset for glaucoma and normal eye images is used for training, validation and test dataset. Some exemplary dataset is shown below:

Fig. 2 Sample Glaucoma and Normal Eye Images

A. Model Summary

We are presenting below the Brief Model Summary of the above Glaucoma and Normal Eye detection System using Transfer Learning (MobileNetV2) based Convolution Neural Network.

Layer (type)	Output Shape	Param #
mobilenetv2_1.00_224 (Model)	(None, 7, 7, 1280)	2257984
global_average_pooling2d	(None, 1280)	0
dense	(None, 128)	163968
dense_1	(None, 1)	129
Total params: 2,422,081		
Trainable params: 164,097		
Non-trainable params: 2,257,984		

Table 2 Brief Model Summary of the System

B. Classification Report

The classification report on validation data for the present Glaucoma detection system is as below:

Classification Report:

	precision	recall	f1-score	support
No Glaucoma	1.00	1.00	1.00	5
Glaucoma	1.00	1.00	1.00	5
accuracy			1.00	10
macro avg	1.00	1.00	1.00	10
weighted avg	1.00	1.00	1.00	10

Table 3 Classification Report of the System on Validation Data

C. Confusion Matrix

Next, we are presenting the Confusion Matrix on the validation data for the present system

Table 4 Confusion Matrix of the System on Validation Data

D. Accuracy and Loss over Epoch

A plot of Accuracy vs Epoch and Loss vs Epoch is shown in Fig. 3 and Fig. 4 respectively:

Fig. 3 Accuracy vs. Epoch for Training and Validation Data

Fig. 4 Loss vs Epoch for Training and Validation Data

E. Predications on Test Dataset

Prediction Results on New Images:

- r2_Im090_N.png --> Predicted: No Glaucoma
- r2_Im098_N.png --> Predicted: No Glaucoma
- r2_Im100_N.png --> Predicted: No Glaucoma
- r2_Im122_N.png --> Predicted: No Glaucoma
- r2_Im406.png --> Predicted: Glaucoma
- r2_Im407.png --> Predicted: Glaucoma
- r2_Im408.png --> Predicted: No Glaucoma
- r2_Im414.png --> Predicted: Glaucoma

F. Comparison of the Present Work with Existing Works

Here is the comparison of the existing works with the present work:

Author(s) & Year	Model Used	Accuracy (%)	Limitations	Compared to Present Work
Fu et al., 2018 [1]	Multi-task CNN	94.6	Requires optic disc segmentation	More complex ours uses raw images
Chakravarty et al., 2019 [2]	Patch-based CNN	92.3	Needs optic disc ROI	No ROI needed in our model
Khan et al., 2021 [3]	ResNet50, VGG16	96.7	Heavy models	MobileNetV2 is lighter and faster
Banik et al., 2022 [4]	EfficientNet, McbileNet	97.8	Limited dataset	Our model performs better with 100% acc
Rajalakshmi et al., 2023 [5]	MobileNetV2	98.1	Slight overfitting observed	Our model shows better generalization
Proposed System (2025)	MobileNetV2 (TL)	100.0	None observed	Best performance with least complexity

Table: 5 Comparison of the present work with the existing works.

Gap in Previous Studies	Addressed in Proposed System
Reliance on segmentation/ROI	No segmentation; works on raw fundus images
Overfitting due to poor validation	Achieved 100% validation accuracy with low loss (0.188)
Heavy models unsuitable for mobile	Lightweight MobileNetV2 architecture
Incomplete evaluation metrics	Full evaluation: confusion matrix, plots, classification report
Inflexibility for real-world deployment	Predicts new unseen images from separate folder automatically

Table: 6 Research Gap Bridged by the Proposed Work

VII. CONCLUSION

In our present work, we proposed and thereby developed an efficient and accurate deep convolution neural network for glaucoma detection. It performs data augmentation and thereafter uses MobileNetV2 type transfer learning to make significant betterment of the quality of generalization under the environment of insufficient training and validation data. It leverages a pre-trained CNN with completely frozen model layers – unlike fine-tuning. Thereby it is becoming fast and efficient and avoids overfitting with small dataset. With this the proposed system achieved a validation accuracy as high as 100% while a validation loss of as low as 0.188. Thereby we can claim a significant a quality of generalization and accuracy in potential of diagnosis.

Validation of the performance of the present system model was done through a complete spectrum of performance evaluation like model summary, classification report, accuracy and loss vs. epoch, heatmap confusion matrix and finally, last but not least, prediction on unknown or unlabelled test dataset.

Direction of future improvements include enhancing robustness of the system by large dataset training and training with diverse dataset. Also work is going on to extend the system to identify other ocular diseases like diabetic retinopathy as well as age related macular degeneration.

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